

RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA: AN OVERVIEW OF OPEN ACCESS INITIATIVES BY INFLIBNET

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ABSTRACT

INFLIBNET centre the inter-university centre of UGC is offering training programmes for ICT Developments in all Libraries, continuously supporting research and development activities in India by open access digital repositories some of them instituted under UGC guidance are ShodhaGanga is a open access digital repository of full-text thesis and dissertations of PhD, MPhil, Project are curated in electronic form, ShodhaGagothri is mirror of research activities in Indian education institutions, all research synopsis are stored for avoiding duplication of research, Shodha-Chakar is the hub of research centers, scholars and supervisors, it connects respectively for discussion on research, IR@INFLIBNET developed it Institution Repository with caliber and planner conference proceedings, Newsletters, various training materials, press clippings, InfoProt is gateway to all Indian scholarly content etc... all these Open Access initiatives of INFLIBNET are enhancing research and development in India.

Keywords: Inflibnet, Open Access, Research and Development, Digital Repositories, Shodhganga

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable development of a country depends upon its entities like research and development etc... India as developing country is enforcing on research and development activities, Indian Government is providing a good portion funds to all the sectors of Higher Education institutions as a major unit which carries research and development activities. In Indian higher education institutions are lacking with ICT infrastructure and skills, as and when the advancement occurs in ICTs. The information providers as well receivers are not able to adopt these advanced technologies in their teaching, learning and research activities. UGC is providing funds to set-up research and development units and scholarships for young scholars to carry out research in Higher Education institutions.

INFLIBNET the inter-university centre of UGC and in its guidance providing training programmes to library professionals on automation, to develop institutional repositories, developed and maintaining open access database and repositories at national level. Users awareness programmes to access and use the generously the open access repository information resource to carry out their research activities efficiently.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THIS STUDY

The main objective of this study is to find out the arena of INFLIBNET centre initiatives in creating and providing open access information resources to Indian researchers. INFLIBNET centre attained tremendous programmes in national level were successfully implemented and actively functioning at present. The objectives of the study follow

- a. To trace out Open Access initiatives programmes of INFLIBNET.
- b. To enumerate usage Of Open Access initiatives of INFLIBNET.
- c. To know process in use of INFLIBNET open access initiatives by higher education institutions.
- d. To identify the method of participation by higher education institutions in information resources progress in Open Access Repositories of INFLIBNET centre.
- e. To make out list of users in INFLIBNET Centre Open Access Repositories information resources.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research as attempted to study through secondary information on Open Access initiatives by INFLIBNET from respective websites of INFLIBNET programme and Projects were exclusively meant for research and development which help the Higher education institutions in month of February 2024.

4. WHAT IS MEANT BY RESEARCH?

Research is a systematic investigation of a problem or question. The process of research implies various components in accordance with appropriate research methodology based on the type of research problem or question. It is a continuous process to bring societal changes and ease the life of human beings. Research allows researchers to pursue their career in their area of interest. There are 950+ universities in India. Each of these universities are involved in teaching and research in a variety of disciplines.

5. INFLIBNET

Information and Library Network Centre is a major nation programme initiated by the UGC in 1991 as a project under the IUCAA (Inter-University Centre for Astronomy and Astrophysics later it become an autonomous Inter- University Centre of UGC in 1996. INFLIBNET is involved in modernizing the higher education libraries and it is set out to be a major player in promoting scholarly communication among academicians and researchers in India

5.1. Objectives of INFLIBNET centre in sustenance of Higher Education Institution libraries

- To promote and establish communication facilities to improve capability in information transfer and access, support to scholarship, learning, research and academic pursuit through cooperation and involvement of agencies concerned.
- To establish a computer communication network for linking libraries and information centres in universities deemed to be universities, colleges, UGC information centres, institutions of national importance and R & D institutions, etc. avoiding duplication of efforts.
- To facilitate academic communication amongst scientist, engineers, social scientists, academics, faculties, researchers and students through electronic mail, file transfer, computer/audio/video conferencing, etc
- To undertake system design and studies in the field of communications, computer networking, information handling and data management.
- To establish appropriate control and monitoring system for the communication network and organize maintenance.
- To collaborate with institutions, libraries, information centres and other organizations in India and abroad in the field relevant to the objectives of the Centre.
- To promote R&D and develop necessary facilities and create technical positions for realizing the objectives of the Centre
- Provide seamless, reliable and ubiquitous access to scholarly, peer-reviewed electronic resources to the academic community in all educational institutions with a focus on services and tools, processes and practices that support its effective use and increase value of this information.
- Develop tools, techniques and procedures for secure and convenient access management enabling users to access information in electronic format from any where, anytime.
- Develop resource selection guides and online tutorials for effective delivery and usage of e-resources.
- Provide seamless and ubiquitous access to scholarly, peer-reviewed electronic resources to the universities
- Facilitate creation of open access digital repositories in every educational institution for hosting educational and research contents created by these institutions.
- Promote digitization of legacy documents and creation of content in e-format (including electronic thesis and dissertations, electronic version of research articles, working papers, technical reports, concept papers, technical reports, annual reports, statistical data, etc.) in universities.
- To generate revenue by providing consultancies and information services; and

- To do all other such things as may be necessary, incidental or conducive to the attainment of all or any of the above objectives.

6. OPEN ACCESS INITIATIVES BY INFORMATION AND LIBRARY NETWORK

The open Access research and development group at the INFLIBNET centre is working for spreading the open access movement in universities and institution of higher learning. The major open access initiatives taken-up by the centre are follows

6.1. ShodhGanga

ShodhGanga is a digital repository of Indian Electronic Thesis and Dissertations of Ph D and M Phil degrees of Indian Universities and Institutions. The thesis and dissertations are known to be the rich and unique source of information, habitually the only source of research work that does not find its way into various publication channels. Thesis and dissertations remains an untapped and under-utilized asset, leading to unnecessary duplication and repetition that, in effect, is the anti-thesis of research and wastage of huge resources, both human and financial.

The UGC Notification of Minimum Standards & Procedure for Award of M.Phil./Ph.D Degree Regulation 2009(Amendment made on 2016) dated 5th May 2016 mandates submission of electronic version of thesis and dissertations by the researchers to universities. As per the Regulation, the responsibility of hosting, maintaining and making the digital repository of Indian Electronic Thesis and Dissertation and accessible to all institutions and universities, is assigned to the INFLIBNET Centre

6.1.1. Objectives of ShodhaGanag

- Provides a platform for research scholars to deposit their Ph.D. thesis and make it available to the entire scholarly community in open access.
- To centrally-maintain electronic thesis in digital repositories of Indian universities,
- To make easy access of Indian doctoral thesis
- To raise the standard and quality of research in India
- To eliminate research leading to unnecessary duplication and repetition that, in effect, is the anti-thesis of research and wastage of huge resources, both human and financial.
- The repository has the ability to capture, index, store, disseminate and preserve ETDs (Electronic Thesis and Dissertations) submitted by the researchers.

The ShodhGanga set-up is using DSpace open source digital repository software developed by MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) in partnership between HP (Hewlett-Packard). The DSpace uses internationally recognized protocols and interoperability standards. It supports OAI-PMH (Open Archives Initiative's Protocol for Metadata Harvesting) and uses a qualified version of the Dublin Core schema for its metadata

INFLIBNET centre, promotes setting-up of institutional and ETD repositories in member Universities using OAI-PMH compliant Institutional Repository Software. It would be possible for Universities having sufficient network and computing infrastructure to maintain their own ETD repositories wherein their research scholars could deposit e-versions of their thesis and dissertations. However, they can use ShodhGanga to host their thesis as backup archives. INFLIBNET centre, besides maintaining the central ETD Repository would also deploy a central server to harvest the metadata from all such ETD repositories distributed in universities with an aim to provided unified access to thesis and dissertations through its harvesting server. Nearly 548755 full text thesis and dissertations are available from 785 Universities.

ShodhGanga encourages the submission of content under Creative Commons License Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-SA 4.0) and also allows using its contents on the same terms unless otherwise specified.

6. 2. ShodhGangotri

ShodhGangotri is an open access repository of Indian research in progress/synopses of Phd, MPhil MRPs, PDFs/ Emeritus fellowship. The word “shodh” derived for Sanskrit and stands for “research and discovery”. This initiative is launched by Honorable Minister of HRD on September 21, 2019. Under this initiative the research scholars/research supervisors in univerrisites are requested to deposit an electronic version of the approved synopsis submitted to the Universities for registering themselves for the Phd, MPhil MRPs, PDFs/ Emeritus fellowship according to UGC M.Phil/Ph.D regulation 2009.

The ShodhGangotri repository reveals the trends and directions of research being conducted in Indian Universities and in other hand; it would avoid duplication of research. The synopsis in ShodhGangotri would later be mapped to the full text thesis in “ShodhGanga”.

As such, once the full-text thesis is submitted for a synopsis, a link to the full-text thesis would be provided from ShodhGangotri to ShodhGanga. As of now 14520 synopses are available from 75 Universities and institutions.

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6. 3. Shodh-Chakra

Research is continues process, the Managing and monitoring research activity is a time-consuming task that requires a lot of effort to aggregate various information at one platform. It is a need of an hour to manage research activity with the use of the latest tools and techniques to complete the research work within the stipulated time. UGC has guided INFLIBNET to initiate the problem and established Shodh-Chakra to help researcher coup with research hurdles.

Shodh-Chakra gateway of researchers for resources is an initiative of INFLIBNET Centre under the guidance of UGC to help the academic community during their research life cycle of a research scholar. The process of using the portal starts with signing an MoU between University and INFLIBNET Centre. The university/institute has to provide valid information of the researcher and supervisor. Further, researcher can login into system and avail the features of Shodh-Chakra. The system will generate login credentials to researchers, Guides/Supervisors and Universities. The stokeholders of Shodh-Chakra are Researcher, Guides/Supervisors and Universities

6. 3.1 Objectivities of Shodh-Chakra

- It provides a unique space to the researcher, guide/supervisor and universities to manage the research lifecycle of a research scholar.
- It works as a digital workspace wherein researchers can collect, store, organize and cite their research work
- It helps researcher to create their profile and manage their preferences
- It provides single point access to all the research needs of higher education institutions in India
- To supply bibliographic information of millions of scholarly communications through the single platform

- To provide research support to the academic community by amplifying the latest tools for conducting research
- To empower and educate research scholars in conducting research work
- To provide interactive platform between guide and researcher
- To understand the research trend across the universities
- To provide a single portal for managing researcher, guide, and universities research activity

6.3.2 Features and functions of Shodh-Chakra

- The Shodh-Chakra creates and maintains research profile of scholar(s) & guide(s);
- It provides access to more than 3.5 lakhs full-text thesis;
- It helps researcher(s) to find out relevant literature from millions of scholarly articles from ShodhGanga, Google Scholar, IRINS, Crossref and other databases;
- Store, collect, organize and manage scholarly resources in a personalized resource space known as My Library;
- It stores information of Scholarship/Fellowship received by a researchers and other administrative details of the researchers;
- Single search box to find out resources using keywords from major metadata fields;
- The Shodh-Chakra provides access to pre-populated Knowledge Resources that are useful sources of information for a researcher before beginning the research work. (ShodhGanga, MOOCs Module on Research Ethics, etc.);
- It gathers information of upcoming seminars/workshops and conferences in all the fields across the country on participatory approach;
- It has a unique feature to mark the favorite resource so that it can be referred in future while preparing the manuscript;
- Reference management tool (Zotero) is integrated with a portal that will help researchers to manage resources;
- It also facilitates researchers to annotate the resources

6. 4. Institutional Repository of INFLIBNET

Institutional Repository of INFLIBNET provides all articles published in all conventional proceedings of INFLIBNET Centre, various training material, press clippings, new letters published by INFLIBNET and UGC etc..

6.4.1 Communities of Institutional Repository of INFLIBNET

Communities under Institutional Repository of INFLIBNET are divided as below:

- INFLIBNETs Publications
- INFLIBNETs Conventional Proceedings
- INFLIBNETs in Press and Media

6.5. InfoPort: INFLIBNET Subject Gateway for Indian Electronic-Resources

The INFLIBNET Centre promotes open access to Indian scholarly content through the InfoPort: a subject gateway for Indian Electronic-resources. InfoPort is designed and developed to serve as a comprehensive gateway to all Indian scholarly content. The gateway open-ups the Indian scholarly content scattered over the Internet through an integrated interface that support search, browse and multiple listing.

The InfoPort selectively catalogues online resources of Indian Origin on diversified subjects available in open access through an elaborate process of testing and evaluation. The Centre proposes to collaborate with librarians and scholars in college and universities in the process of identification and selection of resources. InfoPort is classified according to DDC, indexed subject wise and arranged alphabetically subjects. As of now 1730 electronic resources are available at InfoPort

6.5.1 InfoPort covers Internet resources of Indian origin in the following categories

- Electronic books, journals and reference sources including dictionaries, directories, maps etc..
- Institutional repositories, resource gateways etc..
- Wikis, blogs, Portals etc..
- Teaching and learning website
- lecture note, Magazines
- Audio, Video and other multimedia learning resources
- Libraries, archives and museums
- News and media services including newspapers and online news services
- Websites listing current events and activities
- Websites of Major Research Projects, especially those supported by national funding bodies such as UGC, DST, DBT, AICTE, MHRD, DOT, etc..
- Teaching and learning projects website, especially those receiving Government funding
- Indian publishers and subscription agents
- Listservs and discussion groups especially those having online archives.

7. CONCLUSION

India being developing country has given significance to a great extent to research and development in higher education sector. INFLIBNET centre has taken good initiative under the guidance of UGC mandatory's frame works on research and development activities at higher education institutions and libraries. It is providing training programmes in installation of automation, open access digital repository software, providing and suggesting tools, techniques and procedures for secure and convenient access management enabling users to access information in electronic format from anywhere, anytime through Open access digital repositories.

It is able to avoid duplication of research efforts as per UGC mandated to submitting all synopsis and thesis of research centres of higher education institution at ShodhaGagothri and ShodhaGanga repositories respectively. It is connecting guides and scholars interactions by Shodh-Chakar. All these initiatives of INFLIBNET centre are helpful to Higher Education Institution Libraries in upgrading their information services and facilities. Higher Education Libraries has to adopt and create awareness on use of open access repositories of INFLIBNET in Research Activities of respective institutions.

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